

PROCEDURAL RHYTHM TRANSFORMATION FOR ADAPTIVE REAL-TIME SOUNDTRACKS

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ABSTRACT

We describe a method for analyzing the rhythm of musical material in order to synthesize new variations of the material. This method was used in a system that procedurally generated unpitched percussion soundtracks in "adventure"-genre video games. Rhythmic patterns from musical material are analyzed in order to represent them in a way that can be manipulated easily in real-time. The resulting data representation, the "strength contour," allows procedural generation of transitions between game music states that preserves musical coherence.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes a method for analyzing the rhythm of musical material in order to synthesize new variations of the material, which was used in a software system that composed adaptive, real-time soundtracks for video games. The use of the system in game music design has been described previously [1–4], but not the algorithmic methods with which it generates adaptive music.

The creation of the system was motivated by a common problem faced by game audio designers. Traditionally, game music changes are made as follows. For one game scene, different pieces are recorded that represent different moods or states that occur during it. These pieces have the same tempo and duration, but vary in mood: they are referred to, for instance, as "stealth," "alert," or "battle/combat." In addition, each piece is often divided into several tracks, called "layers," each representing a group of instruments. If the music is written for symphony orchestra, for instance, an audio track of just the strings, another of the brass and winds, and another of the percussion will be made; these separate tracks are called "stems."

During gameplay of the scene, all of these states are looped concurrently, but only one set of stems is audible; those belonging to one particular state. When a change occurs that demands a musical mood change, the audible tracks are turned down and the tracks representing the new state are turned up. This crossfade must be done quickly and can occur at any time. The matching tempo and meter means that all the tracks are rhythmically aligned. Musi-

cal transitions are also made by using only one or some of the stems for a given state: sometimes only the percussion stems are used, for instance, to create a sense of surprise, or excitement, or focus, by bringing the rhythm to the foreground at the exclusion of any melody.

Game audio middleware, like WWISE and FMOD, have evolved to make this process more sophisticated and complex; sets of layers of audio loops can be changed quickly throughout gameplay, allowing the progression of music to branch out along many paths. The size and function of these audio loops is varied, so that transitional segments of music can be inserted between longer music states.

However, this method has deficiencies. Audio artefacts can occur: if a note with a long tail, like a large cymbal, occurred in the new track just before it was made audible, the "headless" tail will be heard. Furthermore, this method does not allow for slow transitions. A slow crossfade between two audio loops will result in a period in which each piece is being played at half volume. This is not perceptually a meaningful way of transitioning between musical material (it could work in specific cases, but not in general).

A solution to this problem that we describe here is to save the music, not as audio loops, but as a database of representations of the music, and then during gameplay to compose in real time by reconstructing music from the data. Transitions are then made by removing notes from the outgoing track, while adding notes to the incoming track.

The question then arises: which notes to remove, and which notes to add? This is the central problem presented in this paper, and the method described below is one solution to it. In particular, we consider which notes, and how many, can be removed from a rhythmic pattern in order for it to maintain an "identity"—that is, for it to be recognizable as a variation of the same pattern heard previously when it is repeated with fewer notes. This aspect is particularly important for game music soundtracks, as musical motifs like rhythmic patterns are often associated with characters or settings.

An experienced percussionist, when asked to repeat a pattern but to "lay back"—that is, to play fewer notes—, will rely on her musical intuition. Investigating this intuition in order to computationally recreate its effects requires an analysis of musical structure, and a method of creating data representations of this structure that preserve important characteristics of the music while also allowing operations that modify them.

The method described below focuses solely on the un-

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pitched percussion instruments stems in "adventure" genre games. While this restriction came from the difficulties of real-time sampling or synthesis of tonal and prolonged instrument sounds, this constraint provided a reason to focus on one musical aspect, rhythm. And, as mentioned above, the use of only percussion stems is a recognizable feature of adventure game music [2, 3].

Timbre is clearly a salient distinguishing feature of this music, all the more so in the absence of harmony and melody. The effects on rhythmic pattern recognition need to be taken into account for a complete investigation of rhythm. This software system, and the method it is based on, do not take timbre into account, and we present our work here as a building block to incorporate with future research, although one whose practical applications were useful in its own right. On this practical note, many of the stems used in the games in which the system operated used the same instruments, so differences in timbre were often negligible.

This method was coupled with a method for recombining beats in a different succession from that in which they appear in the original composition, which will not be described in this paper. Neither will we go into the technical details of triggering the audio files in real time as each beat was composed.

After acknowledging previous pertinent research into rhythm analysis and adaptive video game music, we define the necessary framework in which the rhythmic analysis takes place. We then give an algorithm for analyzing rhythmic patterns from musical material, in order to represent them in a way that can be manipulated easily in real-time to perform the aforementioned transitions in a way that makes them more musically coherent.

2. PRIOR RESEARCH

Research on rhythm in Western music dates back to the earliest treatises on mensural notation during the Middle Ages [5]. Modern rhythm analysis could be said to begin with Hauptmann [6] in the 19th century, evolving into the 20th century vocabulary of time-spans and hierarchies with the work of Komar [7], Meyer [8], Cone [9], Schachter [10], London [11], and Brower [12]. Lerdahl and Jackendoff's book *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music* [13], hereafter referred to as "GTTM," standardized a vocabulary and method of analysis which we will follow in this paper: namely, performing reductions of musical pieces based on a hierarchy of time-spans.

In the 21st century, rigorous mathematical approaches to meter and rhythm have been constructed [14, 15]. While grammar-based models of music mostly include harmonic and melodic parameters, there is some research purely on the syntactic structure of rhythm. Some do not invoke the term "grammar," but still illustrate principles of reductive analysis and syntactic transformation. Levé et al., in comparing several ways to extract a monophonic rhythmic signature from a polyphonic score, suggest a process of rhythmic reduction that is useful for extracting a rhythmic signature from a piece of music [16]. Toussaint compared five similarity measures of rhythms based on reductive struc-

tural analysis, and used the reductions to relate "families" of rhythms [17]. As part of her research on the effects of varying melodic and rhythmic parameters in meter perception, Creel distinguished rhythmic transformations which maintain motivic identity from those that don't, but did not discuss in further detail the structural aspects of the rhythms that evince this distinction [18].

Other research is explicit about defining grammatical models for rhythm. Foscarin, Jacquemard, and others define a probabilistic context-free grammar for the hierarchy of metric subdivisions in a rhythmic pattern in order to determine the proper way of notating the pattern [19, 20], though this model does not relate syntactic units to their function within a pattern. Rohrmeier characterizes rhythmic groups in alignment with meter in terms of the recursive subdivision of temporal units, and defines syntactic functions of rhythmic units such as preparation, anticipation, and delay [21].

Syncopation has been singled out for research in its own right [22–24]. Sioros et al. propose an algorithmic model of rhythm using transformations of syncopation and density [25, 26]. There are many recent studies on quantifying "groove," in which syncopation plays a key role [27–29]. In some of these, a predictive coding model based on listeners' metrical expectancies has been used to formalize a quantitative measure, or "weight," for the amount of syncopation of a note in a rhythm [30].

Computational methods for performing reductive analyses have been postulated for decades [31–34], and implemented with successful results by Cope [35, 36], as a method of synthesis-via-analysis; Hamanaka [37, 38] is an excellent implementation of GTTM.

Real-time, procedurally generated game soundtracks have been a hot topic in the 21st century [2, 3, 39, 40]. The most notable examples have been the procedural implementation of the music for the games *Spore* by Kent Jolly, Aaron McLeran, and Brian Eno [41]; and *No Man's Sky* by Paul Weir and the group 65daysofstatic [42]. Recent research in generative game music focuses on the association between human emotion and musical parameters, primarily using the arousal/valence model to make these associations precise. Various methods of generating music in real time that evoke or reinforce the emotional states experienced while playing games have been studied: adjusting musical parameters according to a Markov-chain-based process [43]; a multi-agent system for algorithmic composition and arranging [44]; a seeded random walk algorithms for melody and sequence generation [45]. Non-real-time, deep-learning methods of composing stems that convey a given emotion, and can be crossfaded according to the traditional method described above, also exist [46, 47].

3. METHOD

The music material considered here is made up of an orchestral percussion section. An example of a piece is given in Figure 1. As mentioned above, this music is played by unpitched instruments, that is, producing sound events that have no discernible single fundamental pitch. However, we will sometimes use the traditional term "note" (which

Figure 1. Ten measures (mm. 11-20) of a score in the style of a game music soundtrack, unpitched percussion instruments only

generally suggests a discernible pitch) to mean “event,” as this feels more natural when referring to a notated score.

To distinguish between two pieces of the music being analyzed, we rely on the repetition of rhythmic patterns. In our corpus, as in much music, these repetitions are never exactly identical, but varied. Analysis of a succession of rhythmic patterns involves both the inner structure of patterns and the distribution of the patterns themselves throughout the score. These different levels of time granularity demand different types of analysis [13]. The latter relies on pattern similarity and grouping, while the former is tied more closely with metric structure and functions of notes within patterns. We use grouping analysis only to determine these functions; that is, at a “micro”-level. We do not consider here the “macro”-level problem of distinguishing patterns or musical sections, although our method does suggest a means to compare patterns and thus identify their distribution in a piece.

Given a piece of music as described above, we first perform a *reduction* on the piece. That is, some notes are heard as elaborating other notes, and an elaboration is heard as structurally less important, or subordinate to, the note being elaborated. These relationships of subordination are hierarchical: a note and its elaborations can be conceptually fused into a single unit, and this unit can then be considered an elaboration of another such unit. This is similar to the grouping mechanism used in languages. A reduction of a piece is then, as the canonical definition in GTTM goes, a “step-by-step simplification... where at each step less important events are omitted, leaving the

structurally more important events as a sort of skeleton of the piece” [13]. From this reduction we generate a new representation for the entire rhythmic pattern, which we call a “strength contour,” where each note is given a strength which represents how much its removal from the pattern will affect the pattern’s recognizability. Using this strength contour, we can then filter out notes in real time by applying a strength threshold: notes with strengths below which will not be played. By increasing this strength threshold during music generation, rhythmic patterns will be played with fewer notes. Increasing the threshold to the maximum will strip down to their barest, simplest structural levels (like a single downbeat). At intermediate levels, the patterns will be sparser, but still, we posit, be recognizable. This provides a method, to be described at the end of this paper, for transitions to be made between musical states as described above.

4. METER

There are different ways of describing a note’s salience in a piece of music. Lerdahl and Jackendoff distinguish between “phenomenal accent,” the sonic qualities that make a note salient “on its own,” (loudness, duration, timbre, etc.), and “metric accent,” which comes from a note’s position within the meter. Meter is the perception of a recurring, alternating pattern of strong and weak beats, such that each beat can be subdivided into subbeats that also follow an alternating pattern of strong and weak [6, 11]. This act of subdivision results in a hierarchy of metric levels, each

Figure 2. a. A metric tree built on a 4/4 measure of sixteenth notes. b. The corresponding metric levels of each note.

containing beats. The term “time-span” [7, 10, 13] refers to the duration of time between two successive beats at a given level; higher levels have longer beats. London [11] argues that, in order to hear a meter, at least two, and preferably three, levels of regular pulses should be heard (he also gives experimental results for the speed of the music that limit the perception of these levels). In analyzing rhythmic patterns, the highest metric level is often taken to be a single measure, as in Figure 2, but it can also span only a part of a measure, or several measures. In this paper we use the term “strength” in place of “accent.” We can refer to either the *metric strength* of an event occurring at a timepoint, or simply the metric strength of a timepoint, independent of any event falling on it; in this respect it is like a potential strength that a note falling on it would have [13].

The “total strength” of a note can now be described as a combination of its metrical and phenomenal strengths, and its value represents the importance of a note in a pattern. It is more than just a linear combination; we must modify the individual notes’ metrical strengths based on their phenomenal strengths, as will be shown below.

While the examples presented below will be solely in binary meter at every metric level, the method is used for ternary, compound, and irregular meters, with proper construction of the appropriate metric levels.

5. RHYTHM GRAMMAR

Modifying a note’s metric strength is done by determining the *function* of the note inside the rhythmic pattern. This function describes whether the note elaborates, or is elaborated by, another note, and if so, in what way. After all the notes’ functions are derived, we create a reduction of the rhythmic pattern by removing all the elaborating notes. The resulting reduction is then analyzed to determine the functions of its notes, and then a reduction of the reduction is generated. This process continues until only one note

Figure 3. Statement, Preparation, Extension, and Anticipation. In measure 2, a is a preparation of b. In measure 3, a is an extension of b. In measure 4, a is an anticipation of the silent beat that occurs at b.

remains. The succession of reductions can be visualized as a tree, as we will see below.

Following [11, 13], we assume that metric perception applies at time-spans of about 1-2 measures and below; grammatical analysis in this case thus applies to this level. Above this, the listener’s metric perception becomes strained, and the grammar does not apply.

Because this grammar consists of elaborations of musical events, it is necessary to first define a base unit, an unelaborated musical event, upon which to build. We will call this a “statement,” notated with an “S.” A statement is the fundamental abstract unit at the root of every reduction; that is, once a pattern has been fully reduced, the result is a single “S” that represents the entire aggregate of musical events inside it. More concretely, a single event occurring at the downbeat of the first measure of a piece that is not followed by any other notes for a while could be considered a statement. Because of the hierarchical nature of rhythms, statements at one metric level tend to be subsumed as elaborations of events at higher metric levels.

We will define three kinds of elaborations:

- A metrically weak beat that groups with a following metrically strong beat is called a *preparation*, denoted with a “P,” following Cope’s [35, 36] terminology (it is generally referred to as an upbeat).
- A metrically weak beat that is grouped with a preceding metrically strong beat is called an *extension*, denoted with an “E.”
- A metrically weak beat that occurs immediately before a silence at a metrically strong beat is called an *anticipation*, denoted with an “A.”

If this example grammar seems too simple to convey the richness of musical functions in a rhythm, we feel that it is not overly reductive. It shows that interesting and nontrivial results can come from a small set of building blocks. More complex models can be substituted for the example grammar while using the same analytical method presented here, with different and perhaps more interesting results.

6. ALGORITHM

We define a left (right) metric neighbor of a note a at level k by the immediate predecessor (successor) of a at level k . That is, given a metric level in which beats have some duration d , by “neighbor,” we are not interested in the notes that fall within beats; we skip these and look back or forward d places to a note on the same metric level as the one we are on.

In binary meter, the left and right metric neighbors of a note are always, in fact, beats at strictly higher levels than the note. This can be seen in Figure 2. In ternary and irregular meters, this is not the case, and modification needs to be done to the algorithm, but this is a technical detail that does not affect the operation of the algorithm itself.

The input to the algorithm is a monophonic rhythm in which the phenomenal strength of each note has been determined, and a metric tree. The algorithm proceeds from timepoint to timepoint, starting with the bottom level of the metric tree and moving from left to right. After handling the rightmost timepoint in a level, the algorithm moves up one level and begins at its leftmost timepoint. The algorithm ends after handling the single timepoint at the top level, the root of the tree.

Figure 4. a. compound rhythm; b. metric strengths; c. phenomenal strengths

For each note in the iteration, compare it to its left and right metric neighbors, and apply to it the label based on the appropriate case.

Let n be the note being considered, and l and r its left and right metric neighbors. Let p_n , p_l , and p_r be their phenomenal strengths, respectively.

- If neither l nor r exist, then n is a statement (S).
- If only l exists:
 - If $p_l < p_n$, then n is an anticipation of r
 - If $p_l \geq p_n$, then n is an extension of l
- If only r exists:

- If $p_n < p_r$, then n is a preparation of r
- If $p_n \geq p_r$, then n is also a preparation of r

- If both l and r exist:

- If $p_l < p_n$, then n is a preparation of r
- If $p_l \geq p_n$, then n is an extension of l

If a note m is a statement (S), place it at the next level up in the reduction. If a note m is an elaboration (P, E, A, or H) of another note n , place n , but not m , at the next level up in the reduction. Maintain a link labeled with the function from the new node to the old node. Continue this process until a level is reached containing only one node. The compound rhythm of Figure 1, its metric strengths, and its phenomenal strengths are given in Figure 4. The corresponding tree built from the algorithm is given in Figure 5.

The resulting reduction is a *rhythm tree*. At first glance it appears as a deformation of the metric tree defined above, but closer consideration reveals that its construction, by equipping notes with function, does not deform the metric tree so much as generate a different topology based on added grouping information. Thus, a rhythm tree is categorically different from a metric tree, though dependent on the latter for its construction.

Figure 5. Rhythm tree

Once a complete reduction has been made, apply a strength to each note in the rhythm by considering its placement in the tree. The details are as follows:

Applied to each parsed event is a strength according to its function. Highest strength is attributed to statements, with weaker strengths given to elaborations. Importantly, the strength function is not symmetric between preparations and elaborations. Preparations expand the time-span of a beat established by a meter. Due to this deviation from the metric structure, and because the new time-span is larger than the old one, preparations are heard as slightly more prominent than extensions, which do not expand the time-span [13]. Giving preparations a higher strength than extensions also aligns with the general function of the music: to create a sense of urgency in the player, adding excitement to the game play. The same judgment, and preponderance in strength, goes for anticipations, which enlarge the metric time-span the same way as preparations.

Follow the links from the root of the tree, node by node, to each leaf. Set each node's modified metric strength according to the rules below, and pass this "parent" strength to its children in order to determine their strengths.

- The root is a statement; its metric strength is not modified.
- If the node is a preparation or an extension, set its metric strength to 1/2 of its parent's strength. If the node is a preparation, add a small amount ϵ .
- If the note is an anticipation or a hesitation, set its metric strength to be the same as its parent's and add a small amount ϵ .

The addition of ϵ values to preparations and syncopations correspond to the salience they incur by changing the expected time-spans implied by the meter. The resulting modified metric strengths, which we can call the "rhythmic" strengths, can be seen as deformations of the metric tree according to the pattern's "centers of gravity." Notes that cluster around strong metric beats are still considered relatively strong, even if they themselves fall on weak beats.

7. STRENGTH CONTOUR

The rhythmic strength of each note is now added to its phenomenal strength to get a strength contour. Figure 6 gives the strength contour for the reduction in Figure 5.

Figure 6. Strength Contour

The strength contour can be used to modify the original material according to a real-time "threshold" value, according to which only notes with a higher strength will be played. Figure 7 shows the compound rhythm of Figure 1 filtered in this way according to the ten values depicted by red vertical lines in Figure 6, starting at .05 and ending at .50. This shows the effect of increasing the strengths of notes on weak beats according to the "center of gravity"—the strong beat—around which they cluster. As the threshold rises, only the strongest beats remain. However, these beats are not reduced quickly to single notes on the strong beats; they retain their characteristic details as well.

8. RESULTS

This method was coded in C++ and implemented as a plugin compatible with game and game audio engines (FMOD, Wwise, Unity). The plugin consists of two applications, an authoring tool and a library for use in the audio engine. Through the authoring tool, the user loads a corpus of precomposed music and sets up mappings between musical states, as described above in the introduc-

tion, and game variables. The precomposed music is written as MIDI files that are played by triggering instrument samples through a sampler instrument (such as Kontakt). Each of these samples consisted of a single attack. The input to the authoring tool are both the MIDI files and the individual samples. The system analyzes the MIDI files using the method given above, and another method (not described here) to determine how to select data from the corpus to play at a given time in the game, based on the current game variables.

Figure 7. Removal of notes according to a time-varying strength threshold from top to bottom, the threshold decreases from .50 to .05, as shown in Figure 6.

To transition between one musical state and another, the strength variable of the first state is decreased, while that of the new state is increased. In addition, the volume of the tracks can be manipulated independently of the strengths, creating more than one way to transition from one musical state to another. The settings of the volume and strength controls for each group can be saved as presets, which can then be recalled during playback. A control for transitioning between presets was added: a "slider" that performs a

linear interpolation between the settings of each preset.

Once this procedural functionality was introduced into the audio engineers' workflow, the concept of a musical transition was quite transformed. Transitions were no longer constrained to occur quickly between states; a transition itself could be considered a dynamic state in itself, in which its parameters vary between two extremes. During game scenes, the system is in a transition state most of the time. Values from the game, such as player health and enemy proximity are linked to transition states and their slider value. Dynamic accompaniment of gameplay is reconceptualized. Instead of being made up of states, with a means of transitioning between the states, it is now made up of transitions, defined by their boundary states.

The effect on the game soundtrack was that the percussion layer was constantly in a state of flux, growing and decreasing in energy, and shifting between musical states. While immediate changes in musical state were possible, slow transformations that followed the gradual change in the player's character's actions and state seemed to be the most interesting and the most promising for further exploration of this method. It must also be noted that some players found the tight coupling of music with player action distracting.

The resulting system was successful enough to be used in two AAA video game releases (details can be provided by contacting the authors). Player response was good, and while this does not, of course, constitute a formal experiment with quantifiable results, it encourages us to use the system to perform future perceptual experiments on rhythmic variation, and to expand our scope of inquiry to timbral effects and other musical parameters. We also plan to release an open-source version of the system in the future.

Audio files of the musical examples presented in this paper can be found at https://github.com/danielbrownmusic/SMC2025_rhythm_examples.

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